

Abstract of presentation at the 2nd Int. Symposium on Augmented and Virtual Reality in Mathematics Education, November 3-4, 2023, Online

https://www.uni-siegen.de/fb6/didaktik/veranstaltungen/symposiumarvr_2.html

The design of educational AR applications for learning about geometry

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Abstract

Augmented reality (AR) technology enhances mathematical learning in multiple ways. It facilitates the connection between 2D formulas and representations with their 3D counterparts, enabling learners to observe 3D objects from various angles and manipulate them using gestures and formula variables. AR also integrates symbolic data with real-world objects. This presentation explores three prototype educational AR applications within the TransEET project, all focused on geometry. The first prototype is an educational AR game for learning about the surface area and volume of geometrical 3D objects. The second prototype involves creating a model of a cup (in 3D) and learning how the shape affects its volume and aesthetic appearance, by manipulating the mathematical formula. The third prototype revolves around learning about parallelepipeds and their characteristics, by exploring these geometrical objects from the inside and outside. Feedback and insights from this presentation will guide further development of these educational applications.

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